

CHINESE SCHOLARS ON THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PRC CHAIRMAN'S INITIATIVE "ONE BELT ONE ROAD"

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the analysis of the opinions of Chinese scientists on the meaning, goals and objectives of the initiative of the leadership of the PRC "One Belt One Road". In their opinion, this is the name of a long-term and multifaceted program of turning China into a global great power by the middle of this century and creating a new world order. It is largely based on materials in Chinese.*

Keywords: *PRC, China, interests, scientists, initiative, economic development, transport corridor, land, sea, belt, importance, regions, program, energy resources, export, import, raw materials, goods, markets.*

Initiative "One Belt, One Road"

The initiative of Belt and Road is connected to the name of current Lider of the People's Republic of China, Xi Jinping (习近平), who came to power in 2013. This initiative arose in the following situation:

1) Economic development, including solving the problem of training young people abroad to become mature specialists in the field of modern technology and electronic. The PRC has made great progress. On this basis, it has become a world factory for the production of various products and equipment, including clothes, modern electronic equipment, and the strategy of the PRC government "Going to the international stage" or "Going abroad" has started to give positive results. [Сидикова М. 12. 19 - 21];

2) China «shyaokang» (小康) has reached the last period of the implementation of the program of bringing the life of the society to the middle level;

3) The growth of the export of products produced in the country and the import of various necessary raw materials and fuels has reached a high level;

4) Reserve of foreign currencies due to the increase, the PRC became a capital exporting country and since the global economic crisis used to activate the purchase of shares and debts of European companies;

5) Due to the annual increase in fuel consumption and the increasing fuel shortage, keeping the country's production rate below 8% is under threat;

6) the PRC's dependence on the Russian Federation for the importation of goods has increased;

7) The increase in the level of social life, the gradual increase in the cost of labor force began to increase the cost of products produced in the country. This began to negatively affect the competitiveness of China's export goods in world markets. As a result, there was a need to prevent this, including improving the logistics of exporting products to Europe and other distant countries, shortening the distance and opening the most convenient routes;

8) The plan to open the shortest and most convenient historical caravan route between China and Europe and the Middle East, i.e., the railway corridor from Kashkar through

Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and northern Iran, has long been unrealized. But for the Chinese government, the urgency of this plan has increased;

9) The need to exploit African markets and natural resources has increased. This need increased the importance of the plan to transform the historical Great Silk Road, which does not pass through the territory of the Russian Federation, a large country, into a modern road;

10) Due to the increase in production and the spread of various harmful gases into the air, the pollution of the waters of internal rivers and canals, and the increase in various wastes, the ecological condition of the country has worsened. Actions taken to correct this situation did not bring the expected results, forcing the government to look for new measures;

11) In order not to reduce the amount of exports, the state faced the tasks of finding new markets from different continents, looking for a new area for effective use of Chinese capital, and further expanding foreign relations;

12) In order to deliver Chinese goods to different continents, the need to open and modernize easy and profitable logistics routes on sea and land has increased;

13) In order to get rid of dependence on the US dollar and the euro for the PRC, it became necessary to convert the Chinese yuan into an international currency and conduct most of the trade relations with foreign countries in this currency;

14) on the basis of the achievements achieved as a result of economic reforms of a quarter of a century, the leaders of the People's Republic of China, who were brought up in a traditional national spirit that contradicted some Western cultures, had the idea of turning China into the largest and most powerful country in the world. This idea was called "Chinese Dream" ("Zhungo Men"), and the time of its realization was set as the middle of this century, the 100th anniversary of the founding of the People's Republic of China.

In September 2013, in a speech at the Nazarbayev University of Kazakhstan, the Leader of the People's Republic of China, Xi Jinping, for the first time called the "Great Silk Road Economic Belt" («Sichou chjilu jingji day» 丝绸之路经济带) forming is China's great dream. Soon after, this idea was highlighted in Indonesia.

Commenting on the concept of the "Chinese dream" in his presentation, the leader of the PRC said that "the policies of the countries will be brought closer together, roads will be opened, free movement of goods and funds will be ensured, economic development will be accelerated on the basis of bringing people closer to each other, and the necessary territory will be expanded for this." [Ma ЮаН. 2014: 6.]

After Xi Jinping's speech, various solemn events and large-scale international conferences were held in the People's Republic of China on the essence and prospects of the "Great Silk Road Economic Belt".

For example, on November 28, 2013, an international conference dedicated to scientific and technical cooperation was held in the city of Urumqi with the participation of representatives of 7 foreign countries related to the Great Silk Road. This conference is dedicated to the formation of the "Great Silk Road Economic Belt", its benefits and prospects. [Ma Yuan. 2014: 136-137].

In May 2014, Xi'an hosted events such as the 18th International Conference on the Great Silk Road, an exhibition on the results of cooperation between the eastern and western regions of the PRC, and an international trade and investment fair. These events were held under the slogan "Jointly building the Great Silk Road Economic Belt is the basis for strengthening interregional cooperation and development" [Ma Yuan. 2014: 159].

On June 26-27, 2014, the international conference "The Great Silk Road Economic Belt - creating a new opportunity for joint economic development, equal use of income and prosperity for its participants" was held in Urumqi.

In September 2014, the conference entitled "IX International Conference of the Heads of the Great Silk Road Cities - Joint Development of the Great Silk Road Economic Belt Cities - 1014" was held. Representatives of 48 cities from 25 countries were invited to it.

The leadership of the People's Republic of China has paid great attention to the issue of wide promotion of "Building the Great Silk Road Economic Belt" in the press and mass media.

Among the works in this field is a large-format color photo album with brief annotations entitled "Shin sichou zhilu - chungshin kaishi de lyucheng" ("The New Silk Road - A New Means of Travel") can be said to have been published. Priced at 198 yuan, this album has been widely distributed abroad. It has become an important gift item for visitors to the PRC.

Ma Yun, the author of the album, noted that "the Great Silk Road Economic Belt opens a new page in history, creating new conditions for people to cooperate and use the roads on an equal basis" [Ma Yuan. 2014: 6].

One can agree with Ma Yun's opinion if the issue is approached from the perspective of the interests, goals and political-economic opportunities of major countries. But it is difficult to find examples of such "equal treatment" in Chinese history. When this country became united and gained power, the emperors who ruled it considered themselves the representative of Heaven on earth and the owner of all the lands on earth. In international relations, the gifts brought by the ambassadors of other countries were considered a sign of obedience, and the gifts they gave in return were considered by the emperor as a favor shown to the obedient. It is safe to say that there is and will be an "equal relationship" in all issues, even in the international relations of the present time, in the relations between the big country and the small countries. Because it is affected, first of all, by the non-uniformity of their economic, financial and technical capabilities. After the implementation of the mentioned measures, soon after the Leader of the People's Republic of China Xi Jinping announced the "One Belt, One Road" (yi-dai yi-lu / 一带一路) initiated. In practice, this is a continuation of the "Silk Road Economic Belt" policy. But the new initiative is much more refined and incorporates Beijing's strategic goals and long-term plans. It can be interpreted in different ways, but it is difficult to know the true meaning behind it. In his own time, Mao Zedong also liked to express his goals with cryptic words in the form of slogans or initiatives, following the tradition of Chinese scholars. One of those words ««Dongfeng yadao Xifeng» 东风压倒西风. Literally translated, it means "East wind overcomes the West wind". But in its soil is hidden the meaning that in the future, China will overtake the Western countries.

The ancient Chinese sages emphasized that a person should keep the true purpose of his work a secret, that no one but himself should know. But they do not express this idea directly with 4 hieroglyphs «man Tyan guoxay» (瞒天过海 - "If you want to cross the sea, don't tell God about it." This word was written by ancient Chinese politicians and scholars «San shi lyu ji» (三十六计 – "36 strategies" or "36 plans") is the first rule mentioned in the work [Stefan.1999: 5].

The dictionary meaning of the word "one belt, one road".

Based on the dictionary meanings of Chinese hieroglyphs, it is used twice in the initiative promoted by Xi Jinping yi word means one, dai带 – belt, lu路 – road. On the surface, these

words do not convey the true meaning of initiation. Nevertheless, this initiative resonated in the language of representatives of different countries. The Chinese associate all of the PRC's foreign policy and relations with this 4-word initiative.

A closer look at this leads one to wonder what meaning and purpose lies behind the initiative expressed in these mysterious words. Based on the dictionary meaning of these three hieroglyphs, philosophical traditions, the content of the economic program to be implemented in the middle of this century, that is, the "Chinese dream", and the domestic and foreign policy of the People's Republic of China in the last period, on the basis of the initiative of the leadership of this country, "the formation of a global economic area that serves the interests of China" It can be understood that the meaning lies. It is known that the "Chinese dream" is to make this country the most powerful country in the world for the 100th anniversary of the People's Republic of China, to create a new economic area where its goods, money, equipment and labor can move freely.

In the speech of some Uzbeks and in the Uzbek-language press, there are cases of using the translation of this initiative as "Bir makon, bir yol". The Uzbek word makon comes from Arabic and is used in the meaning of residence, place of residence, territory, abode, homeland, rank, rank. [Ўзбек тили. 206. Жилд 2. 531]. Chinese dai带 the word can also be used in the sense of a rule in certain circumstances. If the "yiday, yilu" initiative is defined based on these, it gives the enigmatic concept of "one rule in one region". This does not correspond to the original meaning of the initiative put forward by the leader of the People's Republic of China.

According to, a famous Chinese scientist and an active campaigner of the "One Belt, One Road" Wang Yiwei王义桅, in this word yi hieroglyph "wealth, constant increase", dai带 – "equal distribution of wealth based on the Chinese model", lu路 and in the 21st century, it is to interest and support all countries to follow the Chinese model [Vang Yivey. 2016: 157].

According to information on the Internet, the "One Belt, One Road" initiative of the President of the PRC, Xi Jinping, was first mentioned in the speech of the Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi. Later, it was reflected in the official political documents, including the text of publications such as "2015 Socio-Economic Development Plan of the People's Republic of China", "About Government Service". Then this initiative was included as a state program among the important and urgent tasks of the new government of the PRC [Wikipedia].

Causative factors initiative of the "One Belt, One Road"

The Chinese press says that the reason for the initiative of the PRC leader depends on the following factors:

- 1) this initiative includes an area with 63% of the world's population and an economic volume of 21 trillion US dollars and extremely rich natural resources, which is a great opportunity;
- 2) the need to create a new model of international cooperation, to find a suitable way to improve the functioning of existing regional bilateral and multilateral structures with the help of China;
- 3) this initiative "increases the need to ensure the free and orderly movement of economic factors, the effective use of natural resources, the expansion and deepening of cooperation within the framework of market relations, and the need to coordinate the economic and political actions of the countries that are part of the "Great Silk Road Economic Belt";

4) the need to expand and enrich regional relations, establish a new system of joint regional relations, and create a basis for the development of all countries with equal rights and equal benefits [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 157].

Wang Yiwei explains the reason behind the "One Belt, One Road" initiative with the following circumstances:

- 1) "China's reforms appeared as a new achievement of humanity" [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 9];
- 2) "Improvement of internal relations in China, formation of unanimity of the population, and the completion of the work of raising awareness and understanding among citizens;
- 3) The time has come to create a foundation for the formation of a new world open to China" [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 19];
- 4) After the reign of the Song Dynasty (960-1279), the global economic center moved from the East to the West, while the opposite is happening now, and it is clear that the center of economic development will completely move from the West to the East in 2025;
- 5) The fact that the first 10 years of the 21st century was the period of the fastest development for China is a manifestation of the shift of not only the world economic center, but also the political center from the West to the East, and the main burden in this process falls on China;
- 6) It is the increasing need for free movement of Chinese goods, capital and labor [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 9].

Objectives based on the initiative "One Belt, One Road"

Wang Yiwei published his book "Shije shi tungde - Iday ilu de lotszi" ("一带一路"的 逻辑 – "The open world is the real goal of "One Belt, One Road". Explaining the reason for this, the author says that the basis of this initiative is to create a world open to China and based on a new order. Based on this, it should be noted that the original purpose, which is difficult for others to understand, is hidden with the 4 hieroglyphs (words) read as "Iday ilu". On deeper consideration, the title of Wang Yiwei's work reveals to some extent the real purpose behind this initiative. In his work, Wang Yiwei also explains Beijing's strategic plans to open up comprehensive transportation corridors under the Belt and Road initiative. He said that the basis of this initiative lies in the development and expansion of trade relations between the PRC and the countries of Europe, the Middle East and Africa, including the opening of transport routes that pass through the sea and that are beneficial and safe for Beijing, and ensure the free movement of Chinese goods [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 65]. At the same time, the scientist emphasizes the need to do the following practical things to implement this plan.

- 1) formation of a broad economic zone that serves China's interests;
- 2) taking necessary measures and doing practical work to create a global economic area on the basis of countries connected by land and sea routes;
- 3) to see equal benefits and be responsible in international trade relations with equal rights, to introduce the principle of equal development;
- 4) equal use of natural resources, formation of new markets and their control, based on the same rule in the sale of manufactured products, cooperation, increasing the responsibility of partner countries in coordinating and implementing these works;

5) ensuring openness in 5 directions, such as planned trade, freeing of capital movements, raising the political consciousness of peoples, increasing their economic knowledge, bringing their thinking closer together;

6) modernization of the following 6 transport corridors and ensuring their operation in a progressive condition:

- The economic corridor called "New Eurasian Bridge", that is, connecting Kazakhstan-Russia-Belarus with seaport cities in eastern China, Jiangsu and Shandong, including Lianyungang, Qingdao, Jizhao, Xuzhou, Zhengzhou, Luoyang, Xi'an, Lanzhou, Urumqi, Korgos railways passing through oil production areas around Astana and the Caspian Sea;

- China-Mongolia-Russia Economic Corridor, that is, an economic corridor including Tianjin, Dalian, and Manzhouli, a crossing point at the northwestern border of the PRC, connected by railways to the Baltic Sea through Mongolia, Russia;

- China - the economic corridor formed by the roads leading to the Persian Gulf through Central and Western Asia, that is, the economic corridor that includes the roads connecting Urumqi (the center of the Xinjiang-Uighur Autonomous Region), Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Iran and Turkey;

- An economic corridor connecting Kunming, South China, and the countries of Southeast Asia, Singapore, Laos, Vietnam, Cambodia, Thailand, and Malaysia;

- An economic corridor connecting the southern Pakistani ports of Ghara and Karachi via Khunjerab (Khunchilapu), a crossing point in the mountainous border region in the southwestern part of the PRC, and the Pakistani cities of Islamabad;

- The maritime routes of the Silk Road, that is, the economic corridor that includes the waterways from the ports of southern China, the South Sea and the ports of Singapore, the Indian Peninsula, southern Pakistan, southern Iran, and the Persian Gulf to southern Europe and Africa [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 13-17].

According to Wang Yiwei, the tasks and plans under the Belt and Road initiative will be implemented in the following three stages:

1) Full implementation of the tasks developed within the framework of the initiative during the 9-year period from 2016 to 2024 and creation of the necessary foundations for this;

2) starting from 2024 - to complete the creation of a single global economic zone based on the cooperation of the countries related to the Silk Road economic corridors, to introduce all necessary standards for opening and using transport corridors and cooperation;

3) By 2049 - the creation of a single global economic zone under the leadership of the PRC, free movement for all participating countries, equal benefits, equal use of the created conditions, equal communication, equal responsibility and development prospects. citation [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 157].

At the same time, Wang Yiwei said that investment, trade relations and cooperation will be the main content of the "Belt and Road" initiative [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 25], states that enough modern high-speed railways have been built within the PRC, and that the Chinese government is ready to take responsibility for the construction of such roads in the countries connected with the "Silk Road Economic Belt" [Wang Yiwei. 2016: Introduction. 9].

According to Wang Yiwei, in terms of content, the Belt and Road Initiative is "Chinese traditional wisdom thinking" («Chjungguo chuantung chjixuey» 中国传统智慧) reflects the basics [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 157]. In this way of thinking, mutual trust, communication and mutual

understanding between different peoples and countries is aimed at harmonizing "Chinese intelligence" with the thinking of other cultures [Wang Yiwei. 2016. Introduction. 7]. According to the scientist, the initiative is based on the idea of reviving the "zhonghua minzu" (zhōnghuámínzú - "the people of the center of civilization"), which has been the main goal for China for 200 years [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 157].

If the issues and principles mentioned above by the PRC scientist are carefully studied, it is natural that questions will arise as to how practical they are, whether China's economic relations with foreign countries will develop on the basis of equal rights norms.

From the point of view of the benefit of the PRC, the indicated transport corridors are certainly important. But considering the political and economic benefit from them, it is hard to believe that these corridors will give the same result to all countries. Large countries, especially those that have invested more in their construction and modernization, definitely have the upper hand in terms of profit. In order for the relatively small countries to have equal benefits with the big ones, they should have great potential in production, in the field of modern equipment and technology, and in exporting their products, like Japan and South Korea. Otherwise, the equality in the issues that Wang Yiwei mentioned may remain on paper. In addition, the PRC government tries to prioritize its own interests while building roads in foreign countries with its own funds. This is a natural situation, no country solves the problems of others at its own expense, does not put the interests of others above its own. If you look at the history of China's foreign relations for two and a half thousand years, you can find many proofs of this. In the past, Chinese emperors considered themselves the "representatives of heaven on earth" and acted on this concept, gradually expanding their territory by gradually taking over the lands of others. They did not see these actions as aggression, but rather as expanding the scope of Chinese civilization and caring and helping other peoples. Those who opposed the actions of the emperors were brutally punished. From a strategic point of view, considering which of the 6 shipping routes or "economic corridors" ("jingji day") mentioned by Wang Yiwei is the most important and safe for China, we can unanimously say that the transportation corridor along the ancient Great Silk Road is . The reason for this is as follows.

- Shipping of containers by sea-based corridor is cheaper but takes more time. In a certain situation, it is possible that it will be blocked or become difficult for China. According to Beijing politicians and economists, such a situation may be the result of deteriorating relations between the PRC and the US. In a situation where China is growing stronger year by year and aims to become the most powerful country in the world in the future, to establish a new order to improve interstate relations on a global scale, it is possible that a conflict or even a conflict will occur between these two countries.

- From the political and economic point of view, for Beijing, the transport corridor passing through China-Mongolia-Russia to Europe is reliable and relatively safe. However, a large part of the roads within this corridor pass through the territory of Russia. Therefore, the government of the People's Republic of China spends a lot of money in favor of Moscow in order to trade with European and Middle Eastern countries and carry transit cargo through this route. In addition, at a time when the labor force in China is becoming more expensive every year and the cost of products manufactured for export is increasing, the use of this transport corridor will cause material damage to the PRC. At the same time, it strengthens China's dependence on Russia. In addition, the government of the People's Republic of China is careful in its relations with the Russian

Federation. He does not ignore the fact that the relations between the two big countries may deteriorate. Learning from the events observed in history, Beijing does not forget that in a certain situation, the interests of large neighboring countries may collide. Moreover, the use of this transport corridor is not the only opportunity for the Chinese government to have economic relations with the West.

- Currently, for Beijing's economic connection with the West, there is a railway from Urumqi through Alashankou and Kazakhstan, Russia. The section of this transport corridor passing through the territory of the PRC is much larger than the northern transport corridor through Siberia. But using this corridor will keep China dependent on Russia. There is also a railway from Urumqi to Alashankou and Iranian ports through Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan. It was opened in 1990 [Khodjaev A. 2020. 197-207]. But due to the fact that a large part of this road does not pass through the territory of the PRC, Beijing spends additional funds in favor of Kazakhstan for transit cargo.

- From the strategic and economic point of view, the most convenient and shortest transport corridor for economic communication with the West for the PRC is from the industrial cities in the eastern regions of China to Xi'an (ancient Chang'an), Lanzhou, Turfan, Urumqi, Kashkar, Osh (Kyrgyzstan), Andijan, Tashkent and It is a transport corridor consisting of roads to Ankara and Istanbul (Turkey) through Samarkand (Uzbekistan), Turkmenistan, Tehran (Northern Iran), Baghdad (Iraq). Firstly, in the future, it is possible to form a transport corridor connecting European, African and Middle Eastern countries with railways along this corridor, and many regional railways can be connected to it. Secondly, the Beijing government will save a lot of money in transit cargo from this transport route. Because most of the road in this direction passes through the territory of the PRC. In addition, since this transport corridor does not pass through Russian territory, Beijing will not depend on Moscow for trade with the West. But a large part of this transport corridor has not yet been built by railway. For various reasons, the PRC government's long-standing efforts in this regard have not yielded results. But Beijing has not given up on the plan to build a railway in the necessary places and convert the existing highways into modern expressways [Khodjaev A. 2020. 197-212].

Currently, the railway connecting the eastern industrial cities of the PRC with the western border regions has been delivered to Kashgar. One route of the Uzbek railways was delivered to the city of Pop in the Fergana Valley. If the Kashkar-Pop railways are connected through Kyrgyzstan. The following new opportunity will be gained for the PRC.

First of all, the internal roads of the PRC for the transportation of transit goods are quite long. This, on the one hand, allows Beijing to significantly save money in terms of logistics, and on the other hand, creates new conditions for the full use of the capabilities of Xinjiang-Uighur Autonomous Region (historical East Turkestan). On the third hand, in the future, it may be possible to build modern high-speed highways in the direction of the railway, carry gas pipelines, and directly use the fuel and other wealth of countries such as Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Iran and Azerbaijan. Fourthly, if the Kashgar-Kyrgyzstan-Pop railway is built, Beijing will have the shortest transport corridor into Afghanistan. This will create favorable conditions for the use of the natural wealth not only of South Central Asia, but also of Afghanistan.

But the realization of Beijing's plans in this regard depends on the internal political and economic development of the PRC and external factors, including the internal political and

economic situation of the Russian Federation and its attitude to the construction of a railway along this transport corridor.

Of course, the construction of the Kashkar-Kyrgyzstan-Pop railway will not benefit Russia. A large part of the transit cargo carried through the existing northern transport corridor, that is, the KNR - RF - Europe roads, passes at the expense of the southern transport corridor. This situation leads to a decrease in a significant part of the income that falls on the account of Moscow. In addition, the opening of this transport corridor may further strengthen the economic and political position of the PRC in the countries of Central Asia. This situation is also likely to make the Russian government nervous. But he cannot openly oppose the opening of this transport corridor. To prevent this, Moscow may try to take control of the newly opened transport corridor by strengthening the activities of the Eurasian Economic Union (EEU), the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), and including Uzbekistan in this organization. Taking into account the interests of the Russian Federation and the current geopolitical and geoeconomic situation, the PRC government may try to interest Moscow in cooperation in the "Belt and Road" economic program.

The recent situation on the international scene, that is, the political and economic difficulties caused by the sanctions imposed on Russia by the United States and the European Union due to the war action launched by the Russian Federation in Ukraine under the name of "special military operation", Moscow's vision for the construction of the Kashkar-Kyrgyzstan-Pop railway will not be affected. Based on the new political and economic situation and in agreement with Beijing, the Russian government may soften its position in favor of the plans of the People's Republic of China.

As mentioned above, the PRC's interest in the opening of the Kashkar-Persian Gulf and Istanbul transport corridor passing through countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Iran, Iraq is related to the country's internal economic needs, geopolitical and geoeconomic goals. In addition, it is related to the internal needs of China, which has a population of 1 billion 400 million and supplies the world markets with its products, primarily with its demand for gas and oil.

At the same time, a large part of the fuel needed for the PRC is imported by rail and pipeline from Russia and by sea from the countries of the Middle East. The use of waterways for this purpose depends entirely on external factors, including the PRC's relations with the USA, India, and South Asian countries. If these relations, especially US-China relations, break down, it is possible that the sea route will be blocked for Beijing. In this case, the PRC may find itself in a difficult situation. Currently, there are various conflicts between the PRC and the US, India and Vietnam.

Now the relations between Russia and the PRC are in good condition. In the recent past, there have been armed conflicts between them. Moreover, it cannot be said that the interests of two large neighboring countries with different economic foundations and political thinking will never collide. It is already known to everyone that there is an understanding that between countries there will be interests, but not friendship. But these interests are not always the same. In addition, the Russian Federation has a large territory, a relatively small population, a country that exports natural resources, while the PRC is the opposite. Moreover, if you pay attention to the information and historical maps published in the PRC press over the last 30 years, you can be sure that, despite the fact that the border issues between the two countries have been resolved, there is a spirit of

resentment in Beijing towards Moscow. For example, in the historical maps published in the PRC in 1996, it is shown that many places that are part of the RF at the same time were included in the territory of the Manchu Empire, which occupied the throne of China in 1664-1911 and was historically called Qing [Zhungo lishi. 1996. 65-66]. Based on these, it is difficult to say that there will be no conflict of interests between the promising Russian Federation and the PRC. If such a situation occurs, the Chinese government may find itself in a difficult situation in terms of fuel imports. Therefore, Beijing will prevent this and pay great attention to the faster opening of the Kashkar-Persian Gulf and Istanbul transport corridor, which passes through countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Iran, Iraq.

In the following period, the political and economic relations of the PRC with African countries rose to a much higher level. Using the natural resources and other opportunities of this continent is one of Beijing's strategic goals. At the same time, the government of the PRC, as part of the program to improve the environmental conditions in the country, also sees this issue as a convenient place to relocate the production enterprises that have a more negative impact on the issue. That is why Beijing's investment in Africa, the equipment it brings, and the number of Chinese workers there are increasing every year. That's why Beijing is intensifying efforts to create the conditions it needs in Africa, including building railways, ports, power plants, factories, hospitals, and schools. For example, during the years 2000-2017, China invested 40 billion in Africa, the volume of trade relations with the countries of this region was 170 billion. amounted to US dollars. In 2018, the number of medical personnel sent by Beijing to Africa was 25,000. These numbers are increasing every year. China is actively building railways, ports, power plants, factories, hospitals, schools, military cooperation in Africa [Tomberg. 2008: 84-90]. The Chinese government is doing these things in order not to face the opposition of the local people, not to interfere in their internal affairs, not to try to change the existing laws.

In order to strengthen its position in Africa and use the markets and natural resources of this continent, the government of the PRC has been demonstrating its readiness to provide funds, goods, and highly qualified specialists under all circumstances. At the same time, compared to the USA, Russia and European countries, which entered Africa earlier, they are trying to show themselves as good, caring and peace-loving to the local people.

If one looks at China's past territorial expansion policies, especially the ruling dynasty's pre- and post-achievement practices, two different attitudes can be seen. It is possible to witness that the Chinese emperors tried to pretend to be open-minded, caring, peaceful and hospitable to others until they achieved their goal. An example of this situation is the 1700-1758 Qing (Manchurian) dynasty that occupied the throne of China in 1664-1911 and conquered the Jung'or and Ėrkend khanates in Eastern Turkestan observed at the beginning of diplomatic and military efforts aimed at the loss. After the Qin dynasty lost these khanates and took over their lands, the attitude towards the local people was completely different. Let's hope the current PRC government does not.

As part of the "One Belt One Road" initiative, Beijing will try to remove all the obstacles that hinder the development of China's relations with countries in the West, including countries in Africa, and to solve existing problems, and to ensure the openness and usefulness of all transport corridors for China. In other words, for the 100th anniversary of the PRC (by 2049) the "Chinese dream" («Chjungguo meng» 中国梦) provides implementation. If this dream comes true, it is

expected that by the middle of the 21st century, the PRC will become a developed country that will occupy the first place in the world.

Of course, the realization of the "Chinese dream" depends on many unpredictable internal and external factors. It is difficult to predict the future of competition between the PRC and the USA. Another unpredictable factor is the man-made and highly contagious corona virus (coronavirus, "Shinshing guanzhuang bingdu" in Chinese 新型冠状病毒) is called a disease. This disease appeared as a disaster that not only affected the domestic situation of China, but also spread and greatly affected the whole world. No one can tell what the outcome of this unexpected disease will be. A third unexpected event that negatively affected the PRC's domestic situation and reputation on the international stage was Beijing's new policy towards Muslims, including the Uyghurs.

One of the factors that is difficult to predict in advance is that the actions taken to realize the "Chinese dream" may strengthen the great nationalistic spirit of the Chinese people. It is difficult to say what the consequences of this situation will be.

At the 19th Congress of the Communist Party of China, held on October 18-24, 2017, new tasks were adopted to realize the "Chinese Dream" until 2050 [Zhang Peng. 2020: 32]. The Diet passed constitutional amendments that would allow Xi Jinping to remain in office until the end of his life, strengthen the role of the Communist Party, and strengthen the fight against corruption. With this, the leadership of the PRC abandoned the law, which was introduced under Deng Xiaoping, that the top leadership can only be elected twice. It is known that for 30 years, this law created the ground for ensuring political stability and effective implementation of economic reform in the PRC. Based on the practice of the former USSR, the policy of strengthening the role of the party may increase the intervention of local party organizations in the production process, and this situation may lead to negative results. But the question of how this situation can affect the prospects of the PRC is not clear. In 1996-1998, when the author of this article studied the experience of advanced manufacturing enterprises in the southern regions of China, it became clear that the level of development of private manufacturing enterprises without involvement of party organizations was high. On the contrary, it was observed that the productivity of state-owned enterprises directly involved in party organizations is low. Maybe it looks different now. However, the increase in the outflow of foreign currencies in the country, the fact that the government has started to take measures against it, the problems arising in the field of urban construction, including the fact that built houses are not being sold, the closure of some enterprises established at the expense of foreign funds, the rate of production in the country is decreasing from 8%, etc. the occurrence of situations calls for a deep and comprehensive study of the new situation and its consequences.

Based on the above, it can be said that the main content of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative is the creation of an open and profitable global market for China, that is, a global economic area where Chinese capital, manufactured products, and labor can move freely and is provided with modern transportation corridors. lies in creating. But Chinese scientists say that such an economic zone allows all countries included in its scope to use the opportunities created, to carry out relations on an equal basis, and to share the benefits equally. However, based on global practices and experiences of relations between large and developed countries and small developing countries, this equality emphasized by Chinese scientists raises doubts.

Within the framework of the global economic area defined by Chinese scientists, the current Central Asia is of great importance. Therefore, Beijing pays great attention to the republics of this region and tries to further strengthen its political and economic position in the region. At the same time, it will increase investment in all areas and road construction necessary for the use of the natural wealth of the region. Along with the financing, the Chinese government will try to bring its machinery, manpower, modern communication and control tools and technologies to the region. At the same time, it activates lending to the countries of the region.

**One of the original goals of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative
- bringing the Chinese language and culture to the world stage**

According to Wang Yiwei, spreading the Chinese language and culture widely through the establishment of Confucius centers, schools and institutes among other countries and peoples is also part of the tasks within the framework of the Belt and Road initiative [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 208-216].

In most cases, the government of the People's Republic of China has been doing this work on the basis of establishing "Confucius Centers", "Confucius Schools" in various countries, including Central Asian republics, and providing grants to foreigners to study in Chinese cities in social sciences such as economics, language, and literature.

For example, in 2004, the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies (university from May 2020) "Confucius Center" was established for the first time at the suggestion of China [Shazamanov, Sharapov. 2012: 78]. The official agreement was signed in November 2004 during the international conference on teaching Chinese abroad. Soon after, this center was transformed into an institute. This institute was assigned the task of teaching the Chinese language and culture to representatives of the local population in various fields. Studying at this institution was started on the basis of organizing short-term courses. There was no age limit for those who wanted to study. The modern "Confucius Institute" established in Tashkent was the first step taken by China in Central Asia. This event was evaluated as "opening the door to Central Asia" for spreading the Chinese language and culture abroad in the PRC [Ma Yuan. 2014: 177]. Currently, 4 Confucius Institutes are operating in Kazakhstan (in the cities of Astana, Almaty, Aktobe and Karaganda) [Kazinform. a2724590], there are 2 Confucius Institutes in Uzbekistan (Tashkent and Samarkand), 2 in Kyrgyzstan (Bishkek and Osh), and 2 in Tajikistan (Dushanbe and Chkalovsk). In addition, Chinese language is taught in 9 "Confucius classes" and 8 higher educational institutions in Kyrgyzstan.

Until 2021, the Confucius Institute was not opened in Turkmenistan, but Chinese language and literature were taught in universities such as Makhtumkuli National University of Turkey, World Languages Institute, International Energy Institute, International Oil and Gas University, and secondary schools No. 90 in Ashgabat and No. 14 in Sejin. works are being carried out.

The Chinese government, through its embassy in this country, supports Chinese language universities, schools and Confucius institutes by providing necessary support. But there is no parity in teaching the language and literature of these countries in China.

According to information on Internet resources, 475 Chinese Confucius Institutes have been established in 126 countries and regions of the world [Kazinform. a2724590].

According to Chinese scientist Wang Yiwei, who is a participant in a number of scientific projects and actively participates in lecturing at Confucius institutes abroad, 500 Confucius institutes and 1000 Confucius classes have been established in 138 countries by 2016. 51 of these

countries are connected to the Belt and Road Economic Zone. 131 Confucian institutes and 119 Confucian classes started to operate in them. 1,580,000 people were educated in these places [Wang Yiwei. 2016: 208]. To teach Chinese language and culture in these institutes, centers and classes, teachers were trained in 4 higher educational institutions in the PRC [Shazamanov, Sharapov. 2012: 78].

In recent years, Confucius Institutes and Confucius classes have been closed in the United States and some European countries due to local government protests. Perhaps this situation will be activated later.

In this context, it should be noted that in the Confucian institutes and centers opened in the Central Asian countries, there was no training in modern techniques and technology. Those sent to Chinese universities on the basis of grants allocated by the PRC government are also directed to study Chinese language, literature and economics. However, the PRC is a country with great achievements in the field of modern engineering and technology. Central Asian republics have the need to train specialists in these fields. This situation naturally raises the question of why Beijing pays so much attention and money to teaching Chinese language and culture abroad, but does not consider it necessary to train personnel in the fields of natural sciences, especially modern engineering and technology. However, since the last quarter of the last century, the Chinese government, while sending young people to study at universities and other educational institutions in the USA and European countries, directed them to acquire knowledge in the field of modern technology. In short, Chinese youth have acquired knowledge in this field compared to developed countries.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, the following can be concluded:

1) "One Belt, One Road" initiative is the 35-year economic development of the PRC, becoming a world factory in the field of production, gaining great wealth, including foreign exchange reserves, due to the export of its products, moving from a country that imports capital and modern equipment and technologies to a country that exports them. as a result of becoming a major consumer of natural wealth and energy resources.

2) The meaning of this initiation cannot be understood based on the dictionary meaning of the 4 hieroglyphs (words) that represent it. After all, at the base of the thought expressed by these four words lies a deep meaning and strategic goals, that is, the program of turning China into the most powerful country in the world. But some Chinese scholars describe this initiative as an example of "Chinese traditional wisdom thinking". At the same time, they claim that it is based on the goal of harmonizing Chinese culture with the culture and thinking of other nations. Expressing the original purpose in simple and mysterious words is based on ancient Chinese thought, linguistic wealth and philosophical traditions. It can be interpreted differently and adapted to the situation.

3) Chinese scientists say that the original meaning of the Belt and Road initiative is not only the formation of a global economic zone open to the PRC, a common rule introduced, and provided with various modern transportation routes and means of communication through land and sea, or the creation of a new world. consists of Such a world is also called "Chinese dream".

4) The program developed within the framework of this initiative includes Beijing's tasks of eliminating all its problems, removing all obstacles, and opening and modernizing transport corridors that are convenient for free communication with all countries on the Western side of China. As a result of these tasks, by the 100th anniversary of the People's Republic of China (by

2049), the country should become the most developed country in the world, that is, the "Chinese dream" should come true. Of course, the realization of this dream depends on many internal and external factors. They are difficult to predict or predict.

5) The Republic of Central Asia is important for the realization of the "Chinese dream". The PRC government views the region as an important source of natural resources, a profitable market for Chinese products, and an unrivaled bridge in economic relations with the West and the Middle East. Therefore, the Chinese government will continue to increase its attention to the region, investment, use of its natural resources and other opportunities.

6) Chinese scientists emphasize that the new global economic zone to be established under the "Belt and Road" program will bring equal benefits to all countries connected to it. At the same time, they say that all the countries within this region can be connected by modern transport routes and communication tools passing over land and seas, and their products, funds, and labor force can move freely. However, it is somewhat doubtful that countries with different sizes, material potential, and level of economic and technical development will be able to move, develop and enjoy equal benefits with the PRC on the basis of the principle of equal rights within such an area.

7) The framework of the political and economic program under the "One Belt, One Road" initiative, which aims to create a global economic zone, which is considered the "Chinese dream", also includes the creation of the ground for making Chinese thought and language the dominant factor in the future. It is planned to implement this task by establishing "Confucius Institute", "Confucius Center" and "Confucius Schools" and allocating grants for foreigners to study Chinese language and culture in PRC universities.

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